

Complex Compounds of α -Cyano-*p*-Hydroxy Phenacylidene-*p*-Dimethyl Amino Aniline with Hg(II), Zn(II) and Fe(III).

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In our earlier communication¹ we have reported the formation of 1 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes of Hg (II), Zn (II) and Fe (III) in solution with α -cyano-*p*-hydroxy phenacylidene-*p*-dimethyl amino aniline. The present note concerns with the isolation and chemical analysis of the isolated chelates.

EXPERIMENTAL

The ligand was synthesized by the method as described previously¹.

Isolation of the Complexes : 0.1M methanolic solution of α -cyano-*p*-hydroxy phenacylidene-*p*-dimethyl amino aniline and metal salts (HgCl₂, ZnCl₂, FeCl₃) solution of the same concentration were mixed in their respective combining ratios. The solutions were concentrated in vacuum oven and thus the precipitates of the chelates were obtained in the form of sticky mass. The precipitates were filtered off and charcoaled and then repeatedly washed with petrol (60°–80°) to remove the stickiness. The compounds were crystallised from acetonitrile to afford shining coloured crystals. The chelates of Zn (II) and Fe (III) were hygroscopic in nature, so necessary precautions were taken to preserve them in a dessicator. The compounds were practically insoluble in petrol, benzene, chloroform, cyclohexane and carbon tetrachloride. However, they were partially soluble in nitrobenzene.

Chemical analysis : 0.2 to 0.5 g of the chelates were heated several times with conc. nitric acid till the organic matter was completely decomposed. The residues were cooled and triturated well with glass distilled water. In the resulting solutions the metals (Zn and Hg) were estimated as their sulphides while iron as oxide. Nitrogen was estimated by micro-Kjeldahl method while chlorine was estimated by Stephenow's method as modified by Bacon². The percentages of carbon and hydrogen were determined by combustion method. The various results of the analysis are tabulated as follows :

	M%	N%	Cl%	C%	H%
Hg Complex Found	35.61	7.68	12.47	36.19	2.53
C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ .HgCl ₂ Calc.	35.57	7.61	12.56	36.106	2.65
Zn Complex Found	15.23	9.72	16.46	47.58	3.52
C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ .ZnCl ₂ Calc.	15.15	9.78	16.53	47.51	3.49
Fe Complex Found	7.49	11.22	14.22	54.50	4.00
C ₃₄ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₆ .FeCl ₃ Calc.	7.57	11.17	14.13	54.43	4.11

Thus the analytical data found is in accordance with the calculated values.

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1. D. R. Gupta and Y. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 456.

2. H. Middleton, "Systematic Qualitative Organic Analysis", Edward Arnold, London, 1962.

